

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

FERTICOOP

Innovations to adapt to the best available techniques (BAT) in the Catalan cooperative agricultural sector

Develop innovation tools for a better management of manure and agricultural fertilisations, achieving a valorisation of slurry and improvement in the quality of the extensive crops that are produced.

Goal

Advice and give support to the cooperative's technicians regarding the fertilisation and manure management regulation

Results

- Elaboration of a digital platform for manure management.
- Use of the produced biogas for heating the farm itself
- Reduction of emissions and of ammonia and GHG
- Advice farmers about BAT of compost

Activity

- Establishing criteria for an optimal online information management platform tailored for fertilization management planning
- Evaluation and characterization of biogas produced in ponds with flexible cover
- Evaluation and analysis of compost produced by different substrates
- Monitoring emissions in different construction settings and ponds, including different types of pits, covers, soil compositions, and ventilation systems for the evacuation of slurry

Training of farmers about analysed BATs

Follow our journey!

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